

THE EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE TRANSITION TO A DIGITAL ECONOMY: THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK

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Article history:	Abstract:
<p>Received: 8th April 2022 Accepted: 8th May 2022 Published: 20th June 2022</p>	<p>The article discusses the role of the digital economy in the development of society, the current role of information platforms and digital enterprises, legal and institutional changes in the transition to e-government in Uzbekistan, the impact of the Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy in the economy, social sphere and public administration.</p>
<p>Keywords: Digital Economy, Transition To E-Government In The Republic Of Uzbekistan, Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030", Information Platforms, IT-Park, Legislation In The Field Of ICT, One Million Uzbek Coders</p>	

INTRODUCTION

The fact that the state has chosen the path of developing the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of information technology and electronic document management in general. The development of the World Wide Web and quality communication has led to a shift towards "digital technologies". As a result, it has become possible to share and collect large amounts of data, which in turn allows the collected information to be processed, predicted, made based on decisions, and benefited in a variety of ways. For all this, it will be necessary to create a compatible infrastructure, in other words, an ecosystem of global information platforms. However, there is a risk of data loss, business loss, job losses, security breaches and the need for modernization. These issues need to be addressed urgently, as delays in this regard can lead to serious losses. It is not whether the digital economy is a myth or a reality that plays an important role in the changes that are taking place, but how these changes serve society.

MAIN PART

Nowadays, we see how technology is radically changing the public service sector. New business models are emerging, such as Uber, which remove intermediaries and lead to direct customer-supplier relationships. Earlier, similar changes took place in the financial sector and telecommunications. There are also a number of fundamental changes in the industry, as the digital enterprise and the digital image of man - the emergence of robots - can seriously change the functional model of the whole of humanity. The same is true of the digital economy.

The work on the transition to e-government in the Republic of Uzbekistan has played a key role in the transition to a digital economy. Since 2012, many measures have been taken to introduce e-government in the country. In order to make any changes in an

orderly manner, of course, the legal framework must be developed. First of all, Decrees and Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers were adopted, and in 2015 the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On e-Government" was adopted. According to the above-mentioned official documents, relevant changes were made in the composition of the Government, e-Government and Information Security Centers were established. On the basis of Tashkent University of Information Technologies and its branches, courses on modern information and communication technologies, e-government, BPR, ERP were organized and trained for managers and employees of all government agencies. Also, trainings on the use of modern information and communication technologies, interactive services were conducted for the general public.

Technologically, the scale of the Internet in Uzbekistan has developed slowly, with a significant increase in the number of mobile users compared to broadband Internet. Within the framework of e-government, information systems and large databases serving them have been formed. In 2013, the Government began to accelerate the development of a single window system for individuals and legal entities, and launched the Single interactive services portal - my.gov.uz, which provides for the implementation of all public services in electronic form.

In 2017, as in other areas, the country has begun reforms in the field of technology, and from this year in the Republic of Uzbekistan the process of transition to a digital economy has accelerated. The head of state has repeatedly stressed the need for the transition to a digital economy, and the need to develop digital technologies if the state wants to develop. The above-mentioned work in the field of e-government has provided the basis for the transition to a digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The decision must be cited. To date, the country has adopted more than 10

different official documents on the introduction and development of the digital economy.

The most influential official document on the regulation and accelerated development of the digital economy is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 No PF-6079 "On approval of the Strategy" Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 "and measures for its effective implementation." The decree envisages measures planned in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 and strategies for key activities. The Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" is designed to ensure the rapid digital development of sectors of the economy, social sphere and public administration, including the further improvement of mechanisms for the provision of e-government services.

The Strategy sets out the strategic goals, priorities and medium- and long-term goals for the development of the digital economy and e-government in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the basis for the wider introduction of digital technologies based on the UN Sustainable Development Goals and e-Government Development Rankings. does.

Today, the work envisaged in the Strategy is being carried out in the Republic. IT-Parks and IT-Centers, which are an integral part of it, are being set up in every regional center of the country. IT-Park residents are provided with tax benefits. In addition, on-site training of the population in the field of IT, software "One million programmers - One million Uzbek coders" is being carried out.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the above-mentioned data tried to briefly cover the process, in fact, the scope of work done was very significant. Although initially information platforms functioned as information sites, today they provide solutions to many public services as well as individuals and legal entities remotely, without visiting any organization. The ability of the population to use modern information and communication technologies, Internet technologies and mobile devices is growing day by day, especially the COVID-19 epidemic has been a positive impetus to accelerate these processes. The areas of business structuring, education and services are becoming increasingly digital. Uzbek programmers are exporting their software products to the world market. The digital economy, the favorable environment created for technology, is reflected in people's lives.

The leadership and professors of Kokand University are also contributing to this process. Today, the university has several educational platforms, the official website of the university - www.kokanduni.uz, for distance learning - distance.kokanduni.uz, for full-time education - hemis.kokanduni.uz, the official pages

of the university in social networks, the rector of the university electronic exchange of information with students and their parents, university staff and the public through virtual receptions.

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